

TO THE ISSUES OF FORMATION OF NON-LINGUISTIC STUDENTS' MOTIVATION FOR LEARNING ENGLISH

Salakhova Elza Zagirovna

Tashkent University of information technologies
named after Muhammad al Khwarizmi

e.zag2020@bk.ru

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the issue of formation of motivation among students of non-philological specialties in English learning process. The types of motivation are defined and compared, the advantages and disadvantages of each type are described. Practical recommendations are given to increase the level of motivation of students in the English learning process as a foreign language.

Key words: motivation, English learning, non-linguistic faculties, external motives, internal motives, learning foreign language.

INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that the motivation of students of linguistic and non-linguistic faculties, where the number of hours allocated for language learning is less, varies. As many teachers note, the inconsistency of the current living conditions lies in the fact that high requirements for the level of language proficiency of future professionals are not reflected in the amount of academic hours allocated for seminars (within main program), and the difficulties of language training arising from reducing the time for mastering a foreign language, do not contribute to successful socio-economic, socio-professional and socio-cultural integration into the world community. Students of language faculties, on the contrary, consciously and purposefully learn the language - this is the key to the success of their future professional activities. They are motivated from the very beginning to study the language in depth and detail, are fully involved in educational activities, and focused on obtaining first-class results.

DISCUSSION

According to one of the most common classifications, motives for learning activities are divided into "external" and "internal".

External motives (positive and negative) do not motivate as much as internal ones, therefore, they are not very effective in learning process. This can be argued by the

fact that they have a short-term effect on students and are situational in nature. External motives alone are not enough for the educational process to be complete. When comparing external and internal motives, it should be noted that the latter depend on the factors contained directly in the educational activities. By internal motives, we mean cognitive motives, the basis of which is the conscious desire to acquire knowledge, which is satisfied in the educational process. Thanks to the cognitive motive, personal meaning appears in this activity, “thanks to which the study of a subject acquires an independent value for the student; in this case, the process of language learning proceeds much easier, more interesting and more efficient”.

Some working models should be considered, the use of which leads to an increase in intrinsic motivation and, as a result, to the improvement and consolidation of language competencies in students of non-linguistic specialties. To ensure that students are oriented towards the upcoming types of professional activity, it is necessary to produce situations typical for it: work with texts on specialties, writing annotations, reviewing, familiarization with the scientific literature in English, a brief summary of the material read, which has professional specialization, etc. These types of activities are associated with the implementation by the teacher of competent control over the selection of special literature, texts, which contributes to the development of students' interest in language means and, accordingly, has a positive impact on the study of the discipline, reveals the content of the proposed text. Relying on their own professional (extra linguistic) knowledge, students are able to fully perceive the original text, qualitatively characterize the described phenomena and processes, and translate the material into their native language without semantic loss. When students perceive information in context, they are able to evaluate it in relation to their professional activities as previously known or unknown, true/untrue, obvious/not credible, undeniable/unconvincing, and significant/insignificant.

In order to teach the student how to build a speech statement at the level of a simple sentence, the teacher should show him the relationship between the linguistic form and semantic content, the signs that need to be relied on in order to correctly use the adequate linguistic form. When mastered in this way, the student will be able to build other phrases/sentences in a similar way. This helps both to consciously acquire knowledge, skills and abilities, and to form a stable cognitive interest in the methods of action and techniques used.

In order to instill students the skills of independent search and obtaining information, the formation of an inclination for independent deepening and expansion knowledge, internal needs for self-development (development of such qualities as curiosity, diligence, purposefulness), the teacher should, based on

individual needs of students, offer them differentiated additional tasks for the selection of textual and illustrative material, according to independent preparation of brief reports, presentations, writing abstracts, articles, annotations, etc.

Since the society of the 21st century is information and high-tech, it makes sense to use Internet technologies as an effective means of learning foreign language and a means of increasing the internal motivation of students. The Internet information system offers a variety of information resources: web pages of all editions of the world in English, regional sites, the Encyclopedia Britannica, programs and technologies that make it possible to communicate with native speakers, online classes or webinars, web conferences, educational web quests, etc. However, the use of the Internet in the classroom should not become an end in itself, so the teacher should clearly understand what goal he is pursuing, and set clear time frames, the use of Internet resources. Only in this case can we talk about the feasibility and effectiveness of using Internet resources.

One of the important points in the formation of internal motivation is taking into account the self-esteem of students. The lack of adequate self-assessment can lead to dissatisfaction with the results of the activities performed, which, in turn, can significantly change the motivational sphere of the student, the direction of his activity.

In order to form an adequate self-esteem in a student, the teacher should organize external feedback, i.e. control according to the teacher-student scheme (using the proposed questions for self-control). At the same time, the student can identify gaps in his knowledge, skills, abilities, and then the need to eliminate them or, conversely, to feel progress towards the goal, understanding of the educational material, the dynamics in the assimilation of knowledge, skills and abilities.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, to encourage students, the teacher can use positive assessments in oral or written form (praise, encouragement, reward, etc.). It should, however, be noted that frequent incentives lose or reduce their effectiveness, so there is need to focus on the individual needs of students in this matter.

It should be noted that the success of the implementation of the above conditions for managing internal motivation is closely related to the availability of communicative skills of an English teacher. It is absolutely clear that the gradual introduction of the stages of education of intrinsic motivation, as well as didactic and methodological principles, can positively influence the formation of a truly effective system of teaching English.

REFERENCES:

1. [Kassim A. Shaaban](#) , [Ghazi Ghaith](#). (2008). *Student Motivation to Learn English as a Foreign Language*. Foreign Language Annals, 33(6), 632 – 644.
2. Самойлова Е.В. (2015). Актуальные проблемы преподавания иностранного языка студентам технического вуза. / *Перевод в меняющемся мире: материалы международной научно-практической конференции*.